

BLOCKCHAIN IN HEALTHCARE

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Abstract

The amount of healthcare data recorded electronically has increased in recent years. Clinical and nonclinical user including doctors, researchers and educators can apply to medical data storage organisations and access medical data in databases for legitimate purposes easily. While this brings some obvious benefits and convenience to our daily life, troubles also come. The most concerning problem is whether patients personal information contained in healthcare data recordings are likely to be compromised. Though several measures have been implemented in current medical data access systems to protect the patient's information security, such as using the trusted third party to verify the identity of data access applicant, the risk of lost information and invasion of privacy are still high. After success of Bitcoin, a novel, decentralized Electronic Health Records (EHRs), using blockchain technology and gives patients a comprehensive, immutable log and easy access to their medical information across providers and treatment sites with unique blockchain properties and manages authentication, confidentiality, accountability and data sharing, crucial considerations when handling sensitive information. Also enables the emergence of data economics, supplying big data to empower researchers while engaging patients and providers in the choice to release metadata. The main goal of using the blockchain technology to create and implement the distributed network to make sure users have better experience.

Keywords:

1. Key Words

Blockchain, Healthcare, Patients Records, EHR, Confidentiality, Accountability, Data sharing etc.

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